

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

STUDY OF OBTAINING ACTIVATED CARBON FROM RICE HUSK

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Abstract

In this article, the use of rice husk as a raw material in the production of activated carbon has been studied. The chemical composition, carbon potential, and adsorption properties of rice husk have been analyzed. The physical and chemical methods used in the activation process, their application, and mechanisms of action have been discussed. Also, the factors affecting the structure, porosity, and surface area of the obtained activated carbon have been studied. The article examines the possibilities of applying this material in various industrial fields, especially in adsorption and filtration processes.

Keywords: rice husks, adsorption, activation, applications

Introduction

Plant biomass is diverse and is suitable for the production of many useful products. They are renewable products that provide the chemical substances and materials needed by the industry and are predicted to replace fossil fuels in the future [1-4]. Various natural raw materials are also used for obtaining activated carbon, such as almond shells, hazelnut shells, poplars, sugarcane bagasse, rice husks, etc. Currently, ecological problems, waste processing, and recycling issues are becoming increasingly the focus of attention. In this regard, the use of agricultural waste such as rice husk is of particular relevance. The production of various functional materials, including activated carbon, from rice husk is considered a promising direction for increasing ecological safety and efficient use of resources.

Rice is one of the most important agricultural food products in the world. Traditionally, rice is also cultivated in Azerbaijan and used as one of the main food products. At the same time, the result of rice processing in the industry is the large volume (up to 20%) of rice husk, which is a by-product of rice production [5]. Due to difficulties in its collection, storage, and transportation, as well as the lack of appropriate processing technologies, the potential of this renewable biomass is still limited. Only a small portion of rice husk is used as a fuel source for industrial and household purposes. In most cases, it is thrown into rivers or burned, which leads to environmental pollution problems and poses a threat to human health [6-9].

Currently, with the development of industry in developing countries, the use of activated carbon as an adsorbent is rapidly increasing. The raw material base for activated carbon is quite diverse – it ranges from plant

waste to a wide variety that includes brown coal (lignite) and hard coal. The raw material used mainly consists of coals with low combustion capacity and peat. Activated carbons obtained from these raw material sources have high ash content and low strength. Furthermore, the reserves of these raw materials are decreasing over time. Therefore, the search for alternative raw material sources for the production of activated carbon is an urgent issue [10-14].

Experimental

The use of rice husks for the production of activated carbon is of great importance in the production of activated carbons, which is an urgent issue for environmental protection and the search for new alternative raw material sources [15,16]. The main objective of the research is to develop a technology for obtaining activated carbon with a highly porous structure as a result of the thermochemical treatment of rice husk. To achieve this goal, the primary processing of rice husk, optimization of activation conditions, and the study of the physical-chemical properties of the obtained product are set as the main tasks.

The production of activated carbon from rice husk consists mainly of two stages: carbonization and activation. Carbonization is carried out to increase the carbon content and create the initial porous structure. Activation is carried out to create a porous structure and provide the activated carbon with the necessary properties [17]. To evaluate the effectiveness of the activation process, both physical and chemical activation methods were used during physical activation, with steam or carbon dioxide as activators, which react with carbon in the following reactions:

Results and discussion

During the experiments, the effect of parameters such as temperature, gas (steam) flow, and activation time on the specific surface area of the obtained carbons was studied. The results showed that heating at 850 °C allows the production of activated carbon with higher specific surface area values. The optimal activation time is 1 hour. Activation using steam gives better results than activation with carbon dioxide. This can be explained by the tendency of carbon dioxide molecules to react with carbon on the surface due to geometric structures, while water molecules are more likely to react with carbon in the depths of the matrix.

For chemical activation, Na₂CO₃ and K₂CO₃ were used, during which the following reactions occur:

Here, M is sodium or potassium. Reaction (5) plays the role of a regulator in the formation and development of the porous structure. During decomposition, depending on the partial pressures of carbon dioxide, a reaction between carbonate salts and carbon dioxide may occur on the surface or in the depths of the carbon matrix. This pressure changes according to temperature, salt/coal ratio, and the type of salts. The value of the partial pressure of carbon dioxide during the decomposition of carbonates is shown in Table 1.

Table 1

The dependence of the partial pressure of carbon dioxide on the calcination temperature, mmHg

Salt	T = 850 °C	T = 900 °C
Na ₂ CO ₃	9	13 - 16
K ₂ CO ₃	0,2 - 0,6	1,9

The production process consists of the following main stages: carbonization of rice husk at an optimal temperature for the removal of moisture, some volatile organic compounds, and also for the preliminary formation of the porous structure; washing of gasified husks with sodium hydroxide, followed by precipitation and filtration; activation of silica-free rice husk; processing of filtration products into silicon dioxide.

During the carbonization process, decomposition and synthesis reactions occur through recombination, which ultimately leads to the accumulation of hexagonal flat formations – precursors of graphene. The carbonization temperature is the key parameter that affects

the characteristics of the resulting carbonized coal. To determine the optimal carbonization conditions, TGA analysis of rice husk samples was carried out. As shown in Figure 1, at temperatures below 200 °C, hemicellulose decomposes along with the removal of adsorbed water. In the range of 278-536 °C, cellulose, lignin, and other organic compounds decompose. The results of the work [7] showed that when the carbonization temperature exceeds 850 °C, the pores of the resulting coal shrink, which is not favorable for the formation of pore spaces in the subsequent activation process. Therefore, it is recommended to carry out carbonization at a temperature of 500-550 °C [18].

Fig. 1. TGA curve of rice husk in air flow

Carbonated rice husks have a BET specific surface area value of approximately 200 m²/g and are composed of 55% carbon and 45% ash, with silicon being the main component. In the subsequent stages of activation, to create favorable conditions for the formation of pores as well as for the recovery of silicon dioxide, the carbonized coal is subjected to washing with sodium hydroxide. During this process, silicon dioxide reacts with sodium hydroxide according to reaction 7

and is converted into sodium silicate, from which silicon dioxide is obtained by neutralization with a mineral acid. A series of experiments were conducted to study the effect of parameters such as alkali/coal ratio, alkali concentration, and process temperature on the washing rate to determine the optimal conditions for the washing process. The results of the experiments are shown in Table 2 [7].

Table 2

Results of washing carbonated rice husk

T, °C	C, M	Alkali/Coal ratio	SiO ₂ content before separation, %	SiO ₂ content after separation, %	Degree sections, %
100	4	0,4	46	42	12
135	4	0,4	46	16	68
100	7	0,4	46	39	17
135	7	0,4	46	23	53
100	4	0,7	46	37	21
135	4	0,7	46	19	61
100	7	0,7	46	25	49,2
135	7	0,7	46	3	96,1

During the research, the selection of optimal temperature and activating agents for the activation of rice husk resulted in the production of a material with high specific surface area and porosity. This significantly increases the efficiency of the materials obtained from rice husk in adsorption and filtration processes. The conducted research has shown that activated carbon obtained from rice husk can be successfully used in water purification systems for the removal of heavy metals from water, gas adsorption, industrial waste disposal, and as an electrode material in supercapacitors [19-22]. This contributes to the development of technologies that are both economically profitable and environmentally safe.

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